

Recommendations for Swiss Higher Education Institutions to enhance the visibility of their research output

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Editorial

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In the last decade, with the development in Open Science, institutional repositories have become critical components of the scientific ecosystem, and open global platforms aggregating metadata for research output such as OpenAIRE and OpenAlex have emerged. These repositories and platforms play a crucial role in advancing Open Science. They make research more accessible, increase discoverability, and ultimately foster greater collaboration and innovation in the scientific community. Since they occasionally serve as direct or indirect sources for research monitoring, benchmarking, and assessment, these repositories and platforms also contribute to the outreach of institutions. In this way, they support efforts to attract talents and gain funding opportunities. However, as of today, gaps remain regarding the visibility of research output produced in Switzerland. Since the country does not have a centralized system that guarantees a smooth dissemination of its research, Swiss higher education institutions and other research organizations play a significant role in filling these gaps, ensuring the dissemination, findability, proper attribution, and discoverability of the research they produce.

In order to ensure that the research output authored in Switzerland is well represented globally, institutions have taken different approaches. This document introduces 14 recommendations with concrete use prepared by stakeholders from various Swiss higher education institutions and research organizations, including librarians and research support staff. The recommendations include ideas and use cases that address various aspects of metadata improvement and metadata dissemination in local repositories, global platforms, and beyond. They were prepared by volunteer contributors and do not aim to cover every aspect of the topic, but they offer practical actions and strategies to enhance the visibility of research.

The recommendations have a title that is generic in the sense that it is not specific to any infrastructure or persistent identifier. They begin with a description of their relevance regarding the enhancement of the visibility of research, followed by a specific use case that has often been implemented in the institution of their author or authors. Optionally, recommendations contain a discussion and a section with further possible actions.

The first recommendations handle the improvement of metadata at the source, for instance in local repositories (recommendations 1–5). They are followed by recommendations around the curation of institutional metadata or other metadata in global databases (recommendations 6–9). Finally, recommendations that go beyond improving metadata in local and global data sources and that involve direct engagement with authors or direct actions from authors are included (recommendations 10–14).

This document provides a practical foundation for institutions aiming to strengthen their role in the Open Science movement. By adopting these recommendations, Swiss higher education institutions can enhance the visibility of their research output. In this way, they contribute to a more interconnected research environment, where knowledge can be shared and built upon more effectively. With these efforts, Swiss research is expected to be more visible, valued, and recognized on the national and international stage. This not only benefits the institutions and their researchers, but also contributes to the global advancement of knowledge.

1. Provide more and better metadata for research output

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Description

Providing research output with more and better metadata as well as licence information is essential for enhancing the discoverability, interoperability and contextualization of Swiss research output. This becomes especially apparent when registering DOIs for content, for example with DataCite [1], one of the main registration agencies. PIDs such as ORCID IDs for researchers, ROR IDs for organizations and other relevant identifiers – for example, for funding agencies and grants – create a robust network of connections between various entities involved in the research process. These interconnected metadata enable more accurate attribution, facilitate the integration of research output across different platforms and support the creation of a comprehensive PID Graph. By linking works, people and institutions, Swiss HEIs can ensure that their research output is easily discoverable and properly credited. At the same time, standardized and machine-readable copyright and licence information within DOI metadata guarantee that research output can be re-used as widely as possible. Overall, these enriched metadata help to make research output reusable, tracking the impact and dissemination of research, as well as fostering greater collaboration and transparency within the academic community [2].

Use case

The ETH Library runs ETH Zurich's DOI Desk and thus enables Swiss HEIs to register DOIs via DataCite. To register DataCite DOIs for research output published in repositories, only a few metadata elements out of the large DataCite metadata schema [3] are mandatory. However, registering DOIs with just these elements has an impact on the visibility of the research output they refer to. In addition to the mandatory properties, DataCite suggests recommended and optional properties.

Additional metadata are most helpful when they provide unique information and create connections to other resources. Persistent identifiers are the preferred mechanism to ensure reliable, long-term references to relevant information. For example, if you look at the DataCite metadata property "creatorName" (2.1), you find the sub-properties "nameIdentifier" (2.4) and "affiliationIdentifier" (2.5.a), both of which can only contain persistent identifiers such as ORCID IDs, ROR IDs etc. in the form of a (valid) URI. If these sub-properties are provided, no question about the identity of the author or their affiliation arises.

We therefore recommend using the following sub-properties of the DataCite metadata schema (version 4.6) when registering research output. Table 1 offers a quick overview. Please check the DataCite metadata schema for a detailed description including examples.

Table 1. Overview of sub-properties of the DataCite metadata schema (version 4.6)

Property	Sub-Property	Sub-Property Definition
2. Creator	2.4 nameIdentifier	Uniquely identifies an individual or legal entity, according to various schemes.
	2.4.a nameIdentifierScheme	The name of the name identifier scheme. If nameIdentifier is used, nameIdentifierScheme is mandatory.
	2.5.a affiliationIdentifier	Uniquely identifies the organizational affiliation of the creator.
	2.5.b affiliationIdentifierScheme	The name of the affiliation identifier scheme. If affiliationIdentifier is used, affiliationIdentifierScheme is mandatory.
4. Publisher	4.a publisherIdentifier	Uniquely identifies the publisher, according to various schemes.
	4.b publisherIdentifierScheme	The name of the publisher identifier scheme. If publisherIdentifier is used, publisherIdentifierScheme is mandatory.
7. Contributor	7.4 nameIdentifier	Uniquely identifies an individual or legal entity, according to various schemes.
	7.4.b nameIdentifierScheme	The name of the name identifier scheme. If nameIdentifier is used, nameIdentifierScheme is mandatory.
	7.5.a affiliationIdentifier	Uniquely identifies the organizational affiliation of the contributor.
	7.5.b affiliationIdentifierScheme	The name of the affiliation identifier scheme. If affiliationIdentifier is used, affiliationIdentifierScheme is mandatory.
12. RelatedIdentifier		Identifiers of related resources. These must be globally unique identifiers.
	12.a relatedIdentifierType	The type of the RelatedIdentifier. If relatedIdentifier is used, relatedIdentifierType is mandatory.
16. Rights	16.a rightsURI	The URI of the licence.
	16.b rightsIdentifier	A short, standardized version of the licence name.
	16.c rightsIdentifierScheme	The name of the scheme.
	16.d schemeURI	The URI of the rightsIdentifierScheme.
19. FundingReference	19.2. funderIdentifier	Uniquely identifies a funding entity, according to various types.
	19.2.a funderIdentifierType	The type of the funderIdentifier. If funderIdentifier is used, funderIdentifierType is mandatory.
	19.2.b schemeURI	The URI of the funder identifier scheme.
	19.3 awardNumber	The code assigned by the funder to a sponsored award (grant).
	19.3.a awardURI	The URI leading to a page provided by the funder for more information about the award (grant).

Discussion

While we consider the above measures a good way to improve metadata of research output and subsequently its visibility, we are aware of certain limitations.

Firstly, repository owners would greatly profit by having access to a tool or scheduled reports that help them to check their repository for metadata completeness and compliance with best practices on a frequent basis. However, this might prove to be a challenge. While registering DOIs through Crossref, another main registration agency, reports [4] can be used to evaluate metadata, and participation reports [5] help to identify and improve poor metadata, but there is currently no comparable tool for DataCite. Some conclusions might be drawn from the DataCite dashboard [6], where analyses can be downloaded from the organisations and repositories sections; however, this is only partially helpful.

Secondly, to use the ORCID ID, scholars must first register with ORCID, which is often not the case (see recommendation 11).

Thirdly, it is generally challenging to present the affiliation of researchers correctly in repositories, since the affiliation is subject to changes. For example, by the time researchers upload their research output, their affiliation can be different from the time when they were doing their research. Depicting these situations correctly in repositories might not be possible with all software solutions.

Finally, when DOIs are registered via ETH Zurich's DOI system, the format of the metadata is Dublin Core, which is then mapped to the DataCite metadata schema before registration can take place. Due to the use of the Dublin Core format, which has a very different structure, the full DataCite metadata schema is not available. Therefore, registering directly via the DataCite API is worth considering.

Notes

- [1] DataCite, <https://datacite.org/> (retrieved 02 April 2025)
- [2] The text in the description part of this document was written with the help of AI (Microsoft Copilot (<https://copilot.cloud.microsoft/>), 28 February 2025. The following websites are given as a reference: <https://datacite.org/blog/connecting-the-dots-with-datacite-doi-metadata/>, and <https://support.datacite.org/docs/making-and-using-connection-metadata>).
- [3] DataCite Metadata Schema Documentation for the Publication and Citation of Research Data and Other Research Outputs – DataCite Metadata Schema 4.6 documentation, <https://datacite-metadata-schema.readthedocs.io/en/4.6/> (retrieved 17 February 2025)
- [4] Crossref documentation, reports, <https://www.crossref.org/documentation/reports/> (retrieved 03 March 2025)
- [5] Crossref documentation, participation reports, <https://www.crossref.org/documentation/reports/participation-reports> (retrieved 03 March 2025)
- [6] DataCite dashboard, <https://commons.datacite.org/> (retrieved 03 March 2025)

2. Make your repository compatible with international metadata standards

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Description

Interoperability and compatibility of metadata is one of the key issues to enhance the visibility of research output. A pivotal element is the use of international standards on various levels, such as the interface structure (OAI-PMH), the basic elements of the metadata schema (Dublin Core) and the vocabularies used (e.g., COAR). DataCite (DOI-assignment) and OpenAIRE (OpenAIRE graph) build on these standards and extend them to increase the compatibility and visibility of metadata further (in the spirit of OpenScience and the FAIR principles).

Use case

The OpenAIRE (Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe) Guidelines are among the most relevant initiatives in the European context to ensure the compatibility of metadata with the important European e-infrastructure OpenAIRE and between repositories.

For this use case, we concentrated on how to implement the OpenAIRE Guidelines for Literature Repository Managers (v4.0) [1] in the repository, with the help of the OpenAIRE validator.

The implementation of these guidelines in the institutional repository

- ensures compatibility with all standards mentioned above,
- enables repositories to be harvested by OpenAIRE, and therefore to be integrated into the OpenAIRE Graph [2], and thus also into the EOSC EU Portal,
- makes participating institutions fit to provide comparable underlying datasets to the Swiss Open Access Repository Monitor; for details, please refer to “further possible actions”.

How to proceed to make the repository compatible with the guidelines:

1. Get an overview of the requirements your repository must fulfil regarding the OAI interface, and adapt the interface, see Use of OAI-PMH [1].
2. Get an overview of the requirements that your repository must fulfil regarding M fields (mandatory), MA fields (mandatory if applicable) and, if possible, also regarding R fields (recommended); see Application Profile Overview [1]. Adjust your settings either directly in the repository (e.g., by using the right dc fields or by adjusting the metadata themselves), or by means of corresponding mapping/rules on the OAI-PMH interface.
3. Register your repository in OpenDOAR [3], the global Directory of Open Access Repositories.
4. Go to PROVIDE – How to validate and register your data source [4] and create an OpenAIRE account.
5. Check your repository via the OpenAIRE Validator [5] and review the results; see also Figure 1.
6. Make the necessary adjustments and check them again via the OpenAIRE Validator; repeat the process until your repository meets the requirements.

7. Register your repository [6] in the OpenAIRE infrastructure as a data source of the OpenAIRE graph.
8. Get the OpenAIRE validated badge [7] and show to your public that the repository is OpenAIRE-validated.

RULE NAME	RULE DESCRIPTION	RULE WEIGHT	# OF RECORDS	STATUS
I+Iv4 Use of OAI_OpenAIRE Metadata Schema (M)	OpenAIRE expects metadata to be encoded in the OpenAIRE metadata format (metadataPrefix: oai_openaire)	5	0/1	View Errors

Figure 1. OpenAIRE Validator: see the results of the validation for every rule, review the errors or warnings ("Status") and check the corresponding guidelines to see how to adjust

Further possible actions

Provide the underlying datasets based on the OpenAIRE standard to the Swiss Open Access Repository Monitor within the annual repository survey on top of the absolute figures. Beyond the provision of standardized OpenAIRE fields, repository managers will need to define and add an "OA type" field in the repository that corresponds to the "OA category basic" or "OA category advanced" specifications of the monitor (see definitions in "Open Access typology" [8]).

Notes

- [1] OpenAIRE Guidelines for Literature Repository Managers (v4.0), <https://openaire-guidelines-for-literature-repository-managers.readthedocs.io/en/4.0.1>
- [2] OpenAIRE Graph, <https://explore.openaire.eu>
- [3] Register your repository in OpenDOAR (the Global Directory of Open Access Repositories), <https://www.jisc.ac.uk/forms/register-your-repository-in-opendoar>
- [4] PROVIDE – How to validate and register your data source, <https://www.openaire.eu/validator-registration-guide>
- [5] OpenAIRE Validator, <https://provide.openaire.eu/compatibility/validate> [access after login]
- [6] Register your datasource, <https://provide.openaire.eu/sources/register> [access after login]
- [7] How to get the OpenAIRE validated badge, https://youtu.be/Ueuwrxo22V4?si=6_DLKeypX0CVwEfD
- [8] Swiss Open Access Repository: Wiki Repository Monitor, <https://oamonitor.ch/wiki/category/repository-monitor>

3. Use open databases to fill and enrich institutional repositories

Nicolai Hauf (ZHAW Zurich University of Applied Sciences)

Description

Openly available databases contain information on a large proportion of digital publications. Institutions can implement automatic processes that search these sources for affiliated research output and import the metadata in their repository. This solution substitutes or complements publication submissions by researchers that are normally made on a voluntary basis. Consequently, the repository increases its degree of coverage. More publications mean a higher visibility of the institutions' research output, since repository content is regularly indexed in search engines and shared with other services through interfaces.

Use case

In the collaborative project "AURORA", co-financed by swiss-universities, the ZHAW Zurich University of Applied Sciences and the FHNW University of Applied Sciences and Arts Northwestern Switzerland developed an automated workflow for institutional repositories based on the software DSpace to gather affiliated publications from OpenAlex [1] and Crossref [2]. After processing the metadata and performing a duplicate check, a publication record is created in DSpace. In addition, information from applicable self-archiving policies in the Jisc open policy finder [3] is added. This allows us to notify authors in case of green open-access potential with tailored, predefined e-mails.

The selection of the data sources OpenAlex and Crossref is driven by their coverage of research output (various publication types, not only focusing on peer-reviewed articles, and a high degree of completeness), metadata quality and the ability to search open APIs based on affiliation data.

The workflow consists of two main tools, "Publication finder" and "Enricher". Core parts of the published code [4] can be used and adapted independently of a DSpace repository. The "Notifier" is an additional extension developed within DSpace.

The Publication finder searches the OpenAlex and Crossref APIs for publications where the affiliation name or the ROR ID contains certain values. Multiple searches can be performed, considering different name variants of the institution. The returned JSON files are processed, including the elimination of duplicates, a metadata mapping and the merging of information from both sources into one metadata record. The resulting list of affiliated publications

can then be used for an import in the repository after a duplicate check with already existing records. This process helps repositories to increase their coverage of affiliated publications.

We conducted a small quantitative analysis, which is summarized in the Table 1. We focused on works with a publication date from 2020 until 2024.

Table 1. Number of publications extracted from global databases that were (were not) present in the institutional repository

	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	total
Number of publications that were already present in the institutional repository	468	544	496	533	391	2432
Number of publications that were not present in the institutional repository	289	293	352	431	312	1677
Total number of unique ZHAW publications extracted from OpenAlex and Crossref	757	837	848	964	703	4109

The number of publications missing from the repository is significant (40.8%) and shows the value of checking bibliographic databases for affiliated publications not entered by the authors themselves.

The Enricher uses the ISSN information of journal articles to search the Jisc open policy finder API. We define certain criteria to select the best applicable self-archiving policy conditions. The policy must meet certain “locations” [5] and must exclude additional open-access fees or specific prerequisites. Self-archiving of the published version is prioritized over the accepted version. The Enricher extracts the article version, the embargo period, the license and the URL to the policy from the returned JSON file. This information is then saved in a structured form in a metadata field in the publication’s repository record. This enrichment helps repository managers efficiently to inform affiliated authors about their options. Our Notifier extension supports repository staff to send a predefined e-mail directly within the DSpace workflow, using the item metadata. This leads to more opportunities spotted by the repository managers and – hopefully – more opportunities taken by researchers to self-archive, leading to an increased number of publications being available in Open Access.

Further possible actions

The idea to search bibliographic databases for publications can be adopted for other sources that can be searched with affiliation names or organizational identifiers. We additionally considered DataCite. Commercial products like Web of Science, Scopus and Dimensions can be used as well. Searching for publications of individual authors by name or ORCID might be a valid option for some institutions, increasing the list of potential databases to OpenAIRE, BASE and others. The code of our workflow is designed to be easily extendable to further databases.

Metadata enrichment in institutional repositories can be performed for various kinds of information and with different data sources. One possible example is the provision of additional identifiers from PubMed, arXiv, Scopus or Web of Science.

Notes

- [1] OpenAlex, <https://openalex.org>
- [2] Crossref, <https://www.crossref.org>
- [3] Jisc open policy finder, <https://openpolicyfinder.jisc.ac.uk>
- [4] Search for “aurora” at <https://github.com/zhaw-hsb>
- [5] Any Repository, Any Website, Institutional Repository, Non-Commercial Repository or Non-Commercial Institutional Repository

4. Establish mechanisms to improve author data completeness and accuracy

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Description

In research platforms, information tends to be more completely (i.e., values are not missing) and accurately (i.e., values reflect what they are intended to represent) recorded for the author who created the record, while co-authors' details may be incomplete or inaccurate. For instance, an author identifier, which is essential for clearly identifying individuals, could be missing. However, for institutional accreditation and scientometric activities, maintaining a list of publications with complete and accurate metadata for all academic staff is essential, as it serves as a basis for assessing qualifications, research activity and compliance with accreditation standards. In case of lacking identifiers, a possible mechanism to improve the completeness and accuracy of author data is to identify researchers through other metadata, such as their institutional e-mail addresses. This approach helps to ensure correct attribution and maintain data integrity.

Use case

On Alexandria, the institutional repository of the University of St.Gallen (HSG), researchers have unique profiles where they add their publications. When adding new records, researchers ideally link their HSG co-authors to their profiles, which works well for publications connected to ORCID. However, if no ORCID link exists (for the author or the paper), some records remain unlinked. To address this, alternative solutions were explored, with e-mail identification emerging as the best option for improving the completeness of metadata for co-authors and accurately linking them.

A relatively simple case occurs when one record contains both an author identifier and an e-mail address, while other records contain the same e-mail address, but no identifier. The fact that the same e-mail address is used enables clear linking of the records and enrichment of those with incomplete author identifiers. To achieve this, the publication list should be restructured in such a way that each row corresponds to an individual author-publication pair, rather than representing publications as single records. Thus, a publication with two authors would have two separate rows, while a publication with one author would have only one row. Table 1 illustrates the original dataset, where one author in the first publication lacks an author identifier and has

only their e-mail recorded. However, the same author appears in the second publication with both an author identifier and an e-mail address.

Table 1. Initial Publication Data

Publication ID	Author ID	E-mail
00001	10001	E-mail1
00001	No entry	E-mail2
00002	10002	E-mail2

The next step is to create a separate table of authors that contains their author identifiers and e-mail addresses. This can be done using tools such as Excel, SQL or Python (pandas). Table 2 serves as a reference, linking author IDs with e-mail addresses.

Table 2. Intermediate Table Linking Author IDs and E-mail Addresses

Author ID	E-mail
10001	E-mail1
10002	E-mail2

Once the intermediate table is created, it can be merged with the original publication data using a matching function (e.g., VLOOKUP in Excel, JOIN operation in SQL or the merge() function in pandas, a Python data analysis library) to fill in missing author IDs. After merging, the final table (Table 3) completes the process of linking authors to their publications.

Table 3. Initial Publication Data after Author ID Enrichment

Publication ID	Author ID	E-mail
00001	10001	E-mail1
00001	10002	E-mail2
00002	10002	E-mail2

The final step is to validate the results by checking for inconsistencies and manually verifying uncertain matches. This process ensures that all authors are correctly identified and linked to their publications.

After enriching the data using exact matches of institutional e-mail addresses, more challenging cases arise where only partial matches are possible. This typically occurs when a person transitions from doctoral studies to employment, resulting in a change of e-mail domain (e.g., from @student.unisg.ch to @unisg.ch), or when a researcher has previously worked at another institution and provided an e-mail address from there. In some cases, individuals supply private e-mail addresses, making it even more difficult to determine whether the authors should be matched.

For co-authors affiliated with the University of St.Gallen (HSG), additional metadata are used to assign missing author identifiers. Where exact e-mail matches are unavailable or inconclusive, partial matches are assessed, and further contextual information – such as first and last names or recurring co-author groups – is used to support identification. Although these attributes are not systematically applied in automated matching due to risks like homonyms or name changes (e.g., after marriage), they are considered during manual checks to ensure accurate linking.

To further address these challenges, e-mail normalisation techniques – such as removing subdomains like “student” or identifying institutional patterns – can help improve consistency and accuracy. Additional identifiers, such as research units or affiliations, may assist in verifying authorship. Looking ahead, automated processes, including machine-learning models, could enhance accuracy by detecting mismatches and suggesting corrections.

Discussion

Ensuring accurate author identification is critical to maintaining high-quality metadata in research platforms. Exact matches of institutional e-mail addresses offer a solid foundation for linking authors to records. Building on this, partial matches and additional patterns – such as shared co-author groups – can further enrich metadata. While this may slightly reduce accuracy, it considerably increases completeness. Automated matching supports broad coverage, while manual verification helps resolve ambiguous cases and reduce errors. Together, automated matching and manual verification provide an effective balance between completeness and accuracy. Further developing this process using pattern recognition, machine-learning techniques and additional identifiers, such as affiliations or ORCID, can expand both the range of author identification and the consistency of data-linking.

5. Import records from a repository into a library discovery service by import profile and normalization rules

Lino Pinardi (medienverbund.phsg, Pädagogische Hochschule St.Gallen)

Description

For several years now, academic libraries in Switzerland and around the world have been using library management systems that enable the administration of various physical and electronic materials. Thanks to the associated discovery services, library users can find all these resources in one central location. It is therefore essential for the visibility of research output that it is accessible via these discovery services as well. This is relatively easy to achieve because of established metadata standards, such as Dublin Core XML, and existing import procedures, for example for OAI-PMH data providers.

Use case

In Switzerland, the Swiss Library Service Platform (SLSP) [1] is the provider of the national library discovery platform swisscovery [2], which is based on the library management system Alma and the discovery service Primo VE by Ex Libris. The union view and numerous institutional views of this platform are the central entry points to the vast holdings of more than 500 libraries.

The medienverbund.phsg [3] is a member of swisscovery and maintains a view of its own called PHSG Discovery [4]. Research output by the staff of the University of Teacher Education St.Gallen is provided in #Proforis [5], the institutional project and research information system and the repository for publications based on DSpace-CRIS.

A selection of this research output should be accessible via PHSG Discovery and swisscovery, too. DSpace-CRIS contains an OAI-PMH data provider, which can be accessed via <https://proforis.phsg.ch/server/oai>. All publications are bundled in a specific set (col_20.500.14111_7) that can be processed.

The integration of the publications into PHSG Discovery and swisscovery is facilitated by established metadata standards and existing import procedures, as mentioned above. Alma provides discovery import profiles for Primo VE, which enable the automated and scheduled import of metadata from external sources. In addition, links to the resources can be defined [6], and normalization rules applied [7, 8] The latter can be used to customize the records as required by changing, deleting or adding certain tags.

In our case, we need the profile type discovery. There are several settings to fill in, of which the following profile details are particularly important:

1. Originating system: Other
2. Import protocol: OAI
3. Source format: Dublin Core
4. Share with network: checked

In the OAI details, the following settings must be entered according to our example:

1. OAI Base URL: <https://proforis.phsg.ch/server/oai/request>
2. Metadata prefix: oai-dc
3. Set: Publication (col_20.500.14111_7)

If the subsequent click on the button “open test page” reports the status passed and displays a source record and a Dublin Core record, the discovery import profile is working correctly.

If the metadata are not yet displayed as desired, normalization rules can be defined for the discovery import profile. As mentioned, it is possible to change, delete or add tags. The normalization rules are edited in the so-called MD editor. A new rule file can be created by choosing “Rules”, “New” and “Normalization (Discovery)”. Several rules can be combined in one file. If, for example, you do not want to display the resource type code which is used in #Proforis, but the language-sensitive term used in swisscovery, the following rule must be applied:

```
rule "set article"
  when
    "dc"."type" equals "c_6501"
  then
    set "article" in "dc"."type"
  end
```

Finally, the links to the resources must be configured and can be labelled under “delivery”. Depending on the situation, linking is associated with little effort or with more complex requirements. In our example, we are working with a template and a linking parameter. The URL to the resource is located in the tag dc:identifier. If we want to refer to a resource’s handle of #Proforis, we must adjust the matching string with a regular expression, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Screenshot of the Linking Parameter Dialogue Box in Alma (retrieved on 14 March 2025)

Once the discovery import profile is completed, it can be run manually and provided with a scheduler for future updates. For the metadata to be displayed in PHSG Discovery and swisscovery, the discovery import profile must be integrated into a custom local data scope. In the scope settings, “my institution” must be selected as population. In the conditions, the inventory “external data source” must be selected, the operator “equals” and the name of the discovery import profile as value. The scope can then be added to the desired search profiles.

Finally, research output can be found via PHSG Discovery and swisscovery as well (see Figures 2 and 3).

Figure 2. Screenshot of the search and the result list of a #Proforis record in PHSG Discovery (retrieved on 14 March 2025).

Figure 3. Screenshot of the link to a #Proforis record in the View Online Section of PHSG Discovery (retrieved on 14 March 2025).

Notes

- [1] SLSP, <https://slsp.ch> (retrieved 14 March 2025)
- [2] Swisscovery, https://swisscovery.slsp.ch/discovery/search?vid=41SLSP_NETWORK:VU1_UNION (retrieved 14 March 2025)
- [3] Medienverbund.phsg, www.medienverbund.phsg.ch (retrieved 14 March 2025)
- [4] PHSG Discovery, https://hph.swisscovery.slsp.ch/discovery/search?vid=41SLSP_HPH:PHSG (retrieved 14 March 2025)
- [5] #Proforis, <https://proforis.phsg.ch> (retrieved 14 March 2025)
- [6] Configuring Import Profiles for Primo VE, [https://knowledge.exlibrisgroup.com/Primo/Product_Documentation/020Primo_VE/Primo_VE_\(English\)/100Loading_Records_from_External_Sources_into_Primo_VE/Configuring_Import_Profiles_for_Primo_VE](https://knowledge.exlibrisgroup.com/Primo/Product_Documentation/020Primo_VE/Primo_VE_(English)/100Loading_Records_from_External_Sources_into_Primo_VE/Configuring_Import_Profiles_for_Primo_VE) (retrieved 14 March 2025)
- [7] Configuring Normalization Rules for External Resources (Primo VE), [https://knowledge.exlibrisgroup.com/Primo/Product_Documentation/020Primo_VE/Primo_VE_\(English\)/100Loading_Records_from_External_Sources_into_Primo_VE/Configuring_Normalization_Rules_for_External_Resources_\(Primo_VE\)](https://knowledge.exlibrisgroup.com/Primo/Product_Documentation/020Primo_VE/Primo_VE_(English)/100Loading_Records_from_External_Sources_into_Primo_VE/Configuring_Normalization_Rules_for_External_Resources_(Primo_VE)) (retrieved 14 March 2025)
- [8] Optional services SLSP – Serviceportfolio optional Services – 6: Integration of external data sources, <https://slsp.ch/optionale-services/#e-n-accordion-item-1635> (retrieved 31 March 2025)

6. Curate metadata of your institution in global repositories

Teresa Kubacka (ETH Library, ETH Zurich)

Description

Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Switzerland will benefit from curating metadata related to their institution in global databases. Enriching and cleaning existing metadata, in particular by detecting name variants and identifying subunits, contributes to better visibility and findability of research output of an HEI.

During our first pass of curating Swiss data in the global database OpenOrgs, we were confronted with a complex reality of institutional name variants and structures, especially when it involves units governed as collaborations between multiple institutions.

While curating the data of ETH Zurich, we discovered that (1) a relatively small effort leads to identification of most name variants and (2) curating the data fully is difficult for a person who does not know the full institutional context. We believe that institutions active in curating their own data will benefit from a representation that corresponds to their specific needs and structure.

Curation is important not only for the data an institution owns internally (e.g., in a research repository), but also for the data hosted by big external providers, whether commercial or open, as they are relevant for global comparisons.

Use case

Within our work in the project Towards Open Bibliometric Indicators (“TOBI”), we have attempted to increase the quality of the Swiss data in bibliometric datasets by improving the metadata of Swiss HEIs and selected research institutes in the global database OpenOrgs [1]. OpenOrgs is a database of organizations and their metadata, complementary to ROR and hosted by OpenAIRE. It collects metadata of institutions relevant for tracking global research activity, in particular the parent-child relationships between the institutions, and their name variants. Those name variants are identified among the table containing all the institutional affiliations found in the scientific publications indexed in OpenAIRE. The data from OpenOrgs are used internally by OpenAIRE to disambiguate institutional affiliations of research publications.

OpenOrgs is meant to be curated in a community effort. All country curators are volunteers, and the OpenOrgs team provides an initiation session and conceptual support, after which the curator obtains access to the database. The UI allows for a text-based search for existing name variants and their easy attribution to the respective database entity.

In the context of project TOBI, we have contacted OpenOrgs and as volunteer country curators we have undertaken a first attempt to clean the name variations of a subset of Swiss institutions: HEIs, university hospitals and research institutes. Overall, it was possible to attribute more than 6000 name duplicates to their respective entities captured in OpenOrgs. We have observed that some institutions have many more duplicates than others, with a few selected institutions having up to 800 name duplicates, and some only a few dozen. Most institutions that we looked at had 50–500 name duplicates each.

While curating the data, we encountered some challenges that we have resolved to our best ability, but we struggled to do this in the case of institutions for which we did not have inside knowledge. In particular:

- It has sometimes been quite difficult to determine how to map subunits which have more than one affiliation, like a medicine department, joint venture, centre of excellence etc.
- Some institutions have complex internal structures that frequently change over time, and both current and historical names are still present in the database.
- Multilingual name variations, official collaboration documents and unwritten conventions are difficult to apply without the internal context.

Such choices can best be made by people who have good knowledge of the respective institution and structure, and the help of relevant stakeholders would be beneficial. This is why we believe that the best way to improve the data on the national level is for each institution to spend resources on improving their representation in the databases.

Discussion

The curation we undertook is only applicable to OpenAIRE data. However, there are other open databases like ROR, which currently do not yet contain complete information about the Swiss HEIs and research institutions. To see how one can curate data in ROR, see recommendations 7 and 8. For other databases that do not provide a separate tool to curate the institutional affiliations, additional effort on initial data extraction may need to be included.

One limitation of such a curation is that the data are never going to be perfect, the reason being that we are operating on the level of affiliations and not of the granular institutional organizations nor of individual researchers or publications. However, even doing this correctly merely in part helps to improve the coverage of research output in global databases.

Further possible actions

At the time of writing this recommendation, the newest OpenAIRE export is not yet available. A further action to undertake is a quantitative evaluation of how much the curation efforts improved the data findability in OpenAIRE.

Additionally, we believe that it is beneficial to coordinate curation standards among similar institutions that face similar challenges and structures, in order to work towards better interoperability of data on the national level.

Note

- [1] OpenOrgs, <https://catalogue.openaire.eu/service/openaire.openorgs/overview>

7. Add name variants to the records of institution identifiers to improve attribution of research output

Annette Guignard (ETH Library, ETH Zurich)

Description

For the correct representation of an institution's research output, it is of the utmost importance that all research articles from the institution are correctly attributed to it.

Institutions usually have official names, which may exist in multiple languages. However, the official name might not be used by the author, or may be unintentionally modified in the process of article submission, revision, publication and inclusion into publication databases. To ensure that as many articles as possible are correctly attributed to the institution in publication databases, it is recommended that all official name variants plus common name variants are added to the institution identifier record in globally available databases or registries. This will help publication databases to automatically attribute articles to the correct institution, even if the official name is not used.

Use case

Let us assume a search for an institution on Research Organization Registry (ROR, <http://www.ror.org/>) to see how the institution is represented. For example, the *Kantonsspital Freiburg* appears as *HFR Freiburg Kantonsspital* in ROR. Another medical institution with a similar name is the *University Medical Center Freiburg* in Freiburg im Breisgau in Germany. Both institutions are related to their respective universities, the *University of Fribourg* in Switzerland and the *University of Freiburg* in Germany.

The ROR entry of *HFR Freiburg Kantonsspital*, as of 15 April 2025, had no name variants ("OTHER NAMES") included (Figure 1).

<p>https://ror.org/00fz8k419</p> <p>HFR Freiburg Kantonsspital</p> <p>ORGANIZATION TYPES Healthcare</p> <p>LOCATIONS Fribourg (GeoNames ID 2660718), Switzerland</p> <p>RELATIONSHIPS Related Organizations University of Fribourg</p>	<p>https://ror.org/03vzbgh69</p> <p>University Medical Center Freiburg</p> <p>ORGANIZATION TYPES Healthcare</p> <p>OTHER NAMES Labels Universitätsklinikum Freiburg (de)</p> <p>LOCATIONS Freiburg im Breisgau (GeoNames ID 2925177), Germany</p> <p>RELATIONSHIPS Child Organizations Klinik für Frauenheilkunde Klinik für Neuropädiatrie und Muskelerkrankungen Related Organizations University of Freiburg</p>
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Figure 1. Screenshots of the records of *HFR Freiburg Kantonsspital* (<https://ror.org/00fz8k419>) and *University Medical Center Freiburg* (<https://ror.org/03vzbgh69>) in ROR (retrieved on 15 April 2025)

OpenAlex uses ROR to attribute articles [1] to the respective institution. Therefore, a search in OpenAlex may reveal articles that lack the attribution. In order to do so, the articles with a raw affiliation string containing *Kantonsspital Freiburg* can be searched. Then, the search can be refined by excluding institutions to find articles that have not yet been attributed to *HFR Freiburg Kantonsspital*, nor to the *University Medical Center Freiburg*, nor to the *University of Freiburg*. Such a query is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2.

Screenshot of the query in OpenAlex (<https://openalex.org>) to search for articles by *Kantonsspital Freiburg* that are not yet attributed to the institution *HFR Freiburg Kantonsspital* and furthermore are neither attributed to the *University Medical Center Freiburg* in Germany nor to *University of Freiburg* in Germany (retrieved on 06 March 2025)

The query in Figure 2 returned 99 articles. Within these 99 articles four name variants occurred. These are presented in Table 1 along with some considerations as to whether a name is a suitable name variant.

Table 1. Name variants for *Kantonsspital Freiburg* identified by search in OpenAlex and considerations if it is a suitable name variant

Found name variants	Considerations
Cantonal Hospital Freiburg	Use of German city name in English name is not favourable, as the French city name is used in the university name, and furthermore Fribourg is clearly different from Freiburg i. B. (Germany)
Kantonsspital Freiburg	Suitable German variant
Hôpital Cantonal Fribourg	Suitable French variant
HFR Fribourg	Suitable variant or acronym

Another route to find name variants is to analyse the names on the institution website (presumably the official ones). This route provides the four name variants for *Kantonsspital Freiburg* displayed in Table 2.

Table 2. Name variants for Kantonsspital Freiburg taken from website (<https://www.h-fr.ch/de>, accessed on 06 March 2025) and consideration if it is a suitable name variant

Found name variants	Considerations
HFR Freiburg – Kantonsspital	Apart from the hyphen, this is the name used in ROR (https://ror.org/00fz8k419)
HFR Fribourg – Hôpital cantonal	Suitable French variant
hôpital fribourgeois (HFR) Hôpital de formation universitaire et de recherche	Suitable French variant
freiburger spital (HFR) Universitäres Lehr- und Forschungsspital	Suitable German variant

Once the suitable name variants are found, they have to be evaluated in terms of, e.g., accuracy, desirability, uniqueness and maybe other aspects. The best-suited name variants can then be suggested to be added to ROR by filling in a curation request (<http://curation-request.ror.org/>) for each variant. For bulk update of institutional metadata, see recommendation 8.

In summary, here are the recommendations to improve the ROR record of an institution:

1. Add the official institution name in all relevant languages (especially English and national languages) to the ROR record;
2. If there is no official institution name, e.g., in English, add an unofficial variant of the name to the ROR record;
3. Add other name variants that are used in the affiliation of articles. Identify those by searching and analysing existing records in OpenAlex – as described above.

Further possible actions

In addition, the tool Works-magnet (<https://works-magnet.esr.gouv.fr/>) can be used to analyse raw affiliation strings and to improve the institutional attribution in OpenAlex.

Note

[1] In OpenAlex, the term “works” is used and does not exclusively include publications of type “article.”

8. Look for possibilities to bulk update your institutional metadata in global research organization databases

Simon Willemin (ETH Library, ETH Zurich),
Christophe Schneble (Vice Rectorate of Research, University of Bern),
Christian Muheim (medienverbund.phsg, Pädagogische Hochschule St.Gallen)

Description

Global databases providing persistent identifiers of research organizations are an important source for global research analytics. The better an institution is represented in such a data source, the better it will feature in the tools (publication databases, monitoring dashboards, submission forms, etc.) that use institutional identifiers from that source. Hence, it is important for institutions to ensure that they are included and represented according to the scope of these databases. If there are gaps, the sooner the data are improved, the better.

Community-led global open platforms such as ROR (Research Organization Registry) [1], OpenOrgs and Wikidata provide opportunities to curate the data manually. In some cases, the required curation affects dozens of records, making manual curation inefficient. Finding ways to update data in bulk helps improve the data, while reducing the time and risk of human error that can occur if records are curated one by one. Curating the data in such a way not only helps to improve openly available data, but also improves the interoperability between locally and globally available data.

Use case

ETH Zurich and the St.Gallen University of Teacher Education are parent organizations that include organizational units such as departments, laboratories and research institutes. Depending on the scope of the global databases, such sub-units may or may not be included. ROR's FAQs describe that sub-units such as laboratories and research institutes are in scope, whereas departments within organizations are out of scope, because ROR is not focused on mapping departments within institutions [2].

ETH Zurich is the parent organization of more than 100 institutes and other research units (outside of departments) that appear to be in scope of ROR. However, as of February 2025, the number of child organizations recorded by ROR was smaller than five for ETH Zurich and the St.Gallen University of Teacher Education. It would have been possible to curate ROR by submitting a change request for each child organization (see recommendation 7 for an example). Instead of updating ROR manually for each child organization, it is possible to update the data in bulk. To do so, we filled in a spreadsheet with metadata associated with the child organizations, including name variations, acronyms, websites and establishment years [3]. We sent this spreadsheet to ROR by e-mail, and a ticket was opened accordingly [4, 5]. Consequently, the number of child organizational units for ETH Zurich and St.Gallen University of Teacher Education has risen from less than five to 105, and to 17.

In accordance with ROR's criteria, organizational units that are primarily administrative in nature were rejected [6]. The same is valid for organizational units that are located at a lower hierarchical level [7]. In contrast, all organizational units that are at a first hierarchy level and that met the relevant ROR criteria were added [8].

The records added during this update have all been given a persistent identifier that will facilitate the identification of related research output and improve their visibility.

Discussion

This update was a one-off, and one can think of ways to ensure that ROR adapts to changes in the organizational landscape over time. One can consider an annual update or (semi-)automated processes to ensure that changes in the institutions are reflected in ROR.

Mapping organizations at a more granular level not only increases the visibility of the research output of the respective organizations, but also facilitates benchmarking between institutions. To align these opportunities with current efforts to improve research assessment, we recommend supporting initiatives to increase metrics literacy and the responsible use of quantitative indicators as advocated by DORA (San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment) and CoARA (Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment).

Notes

- [1] ROR, <https://ror.org>
- [2] Is my organization in scope for ROR?, <https://ror.org/about/faqs/#is-my-organization-in-scope-for-ror>
- [3] Bulk requests, <https://ror.org/registry/#bulk-requests>
- [4] Project: New Records from ETH Zurich, <https://github.com/ror-community/ror-updates/issues/18965>
- [5] Project: Pädagogische Hochschule St.Gallen – <https://ror.org/05m37v666>, <https://github.com/ror-community/ror-updates/issues/17203>
- [6] The ROR reviewer comments: "This [submitted organizational unit] would correspond to the administration of <https://ror.org/05m37v666> [St.Gallen University of Teacher Education] and this is out of scope" (<https://github.com/ror-community/ror-updates/issues/19387>).
- [7] The ROR reviewer comments: "Within ROR's scope, we would only add the parent institute [of the submitted organizational unit] here" (<https://github.com/ror-community/ror-updates/issues/19373>).
- [8] The ROR reviewer comments: "[The submitted organizational unit] [f]unds and employs researchers. Solid affiliation usage. Should be added" (<https://github.com/ror-community/ror-updates/issues/19383>).

9. Explore the output associated with your institution in global databases to identify potential for improvement

Simon Willemin (ETH Library, ETH Zurich)

Description

Open global scholarly metadata databases for metadata such as OpenAIRE Graph and OpenAlex are used in various contexts such as communication (monitoring dashboards), evaluation (research assessment), exploration (knowledge discovery) and research (quantitative science studies). These databases are continuously expanding with the integration of new research output and improving with more or with enriched metadata. Institutions can actively contribute to this expansion and improvement. For instance, they can ensure that the records available locally in their institutional repository are referenced using persistent identifiers (e.g., DOI, ORCID ID, ROR ID) and are available for ingestion in global databases. However, given the complexity of the aggregation process underlying global databases, providing persistent identifiers and accurate metadata in institutional repositories may not be sufficient to guarantee that the records available locally are ingested as expected. Complementary to providing high-quality data and metadata, institutions will benefit from exploring the institutional output available in global databases. The exploration of this output helps one not only to understand the data-dissemination process better, but also to correct potential errors and hence improve the visibility of the research output globally.

Use case

We explored the articles attributed to ETH Zurich in OpenAIRE Graph [1]. Using API queries and paging, we extracted research products of type “article” attributed to “ETH Zurich” for the year 2024 [2]. The data were extracted on 3 March 2025, and the response provided 6,791 records.

To investigate the data, we grouped records by their title. It appeared that 362 titles (5.3%) are present twice. In most cases, this is not due to different articles with the same title, but to articles that have not been deduplicated. Part of the titles appears both under a record with a Handle as a persistent identifier for location and under a record with a DOI as a persistent identifier for location. Table 1 provides the metadata of three articles, each of which are referenced twice instead of once in OpenAIRE Graph.

After exchanges both with the OpenAIRE Graph team and the local repository manager at ETH Zurich, it appears that duplicate records such as those in Table 1 do not have to do with the presence

of multiple persistent identifiers (i.e., DOIs and Handle), but with the formatting of the authors' names: One of the duplicate records, usually the one with DOIs, includes the author's ORCID ID (e.g., “0000-0002-1825-0097”) and the author's name (e.g., “Josiah Carberry”) in separate fields, while the other record, usually the one with the Handle, only has empty author ORCID IDs (e.g., “”), and the missing information appears in the author's name (e.g., “Carberry, Josiah; id_orcid0000-0002-1825-0097”). This harvesting issue stems from an earlier version of the OpenAIRE metadata scheme that did not allow for sub-fields such as ORCID for authors, and an update in the metadata scheme (v. 4.1) [3; see also recommendation 2] that allows more features and that could not yet be implemented in the local repository of ETH Zurich. Once the implementation of the updated scheme will happen, the authors' names in duplicate records will be close enough to be matched, and the records will hopefully be deduplicated.

Table 1. Articles from ETH Zurich receiving multiple identifiers in OpenAIRE Graph

OpenAIRE identifier	Main title	DOIs	Handle
od_____150::b0e72d83970ab160632d4518aea1d3eb	Acoustic scattering of a sequential combustor [...]		http://hdl.handle.net/20.500.11850/682599
doi_dedup____:8c707b40c95cc85c7cd5824598e48bbd	Acoustic scattering of a sequential combustor [...]	doi.org/10.1016/j.proci.2024.10538; doi.org/10.3929/ethz-b-000682599	
od_____150::99a7c6d85912c23cb569eb882028856d	Algebraic surrogate-based flexibility analysis [...]		http://hdl.handle.net/20.500.11850/666223
doi_dedup____:8247e3e78b085578d9def189c53232c3	Algebraic surrogate-based flexibility analysis [...]	doi.org/10.3929/ethz-b-000666223; doi.org/10.1016/j.compchemeng.2024.108630	
od_____150::9122c3634c8a50165e12dee6098d9961	Aptamer Renaissance for Neurochemical Biosensing		http://hdl.handle.net/20.500.11850/658776
doi_dedup____:2706630735936ffa271848dd4cfab218	Aptamer Renaissance for Neurochemical Biosensing	doi.org/10.3929/ethz-b-000658776; doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.3c09576	

Discussion

The same analysis can be applied to other institutions and databases, enabling the identification of similar issues. For instance, looking for duplicate titles of articles from the University of Lucerne in the database OpenAlex [4] led to the identification of 81 titles that appeared more than once in the considered data, totalling 85 records out of 1,943 (4.4%). The duplicated articles were partly due to the use of Zenodo as the main repository for the institutional output. The DOI provided through Zenodo (starting with “doi.org/10.5281”) and the DOI provided by the publisher were not deduplicated during the aggregation process [5, slides 37–38, 58–70].

The analysis may also uncover issues that are not related to deduplication. Looking for articles from the University of Neuchâtel with identical titles in OpenAlex [4] led to the identification of 82 records out of 2,565 (3.2%) whose title started with “Data for EMSL Project” and that appeared under the publication type “article” instead of “dataset.” Further investigation suggested that the misattribution was specific to the considered database. The error could hence be reported to its inferred source [5, slides 29–30, 55–56].

These examples involve articles that have not been deduplicated and publication types that have been misattributed. They result in a greater number of articles being attributed to the considered institutions. While one can expect that such issues will be corrected in the middle or longer term, in the shorter term they may not always be easily resolved. Hence, such an investigation not only allows analysts to identify the potential for improvement, but also helps to clean the data before performing an analysis, and to interpret responsibly the insights gained from dashboards and further tools directly derived from the considered data sources.

Further possible actions

Duplicate titles are one option for exploration. Investigating other metadata such as the institutional attribution can uncover further opportunities for improvement and curation, as in the use cases described in recommendations 7 and 10.

Notes

- [1] Manghi, P., Atzori, C., Bardi, A., Baglioni, M., Dimitropoulos, H., La Bruzzo, S., Foufoulas, I., Mannocci, A., Horst, M., Iatropoulou, K., Kokogiannaki, A., De Bonis, M., Artini, M., Lempesis, A., Ioannidis, A., Manola, N., Principe, P., Vergoulis, T., & Chatzopoulos, S. (2025). *OpenAIRE Graph Dataset (9.0.1)* [Data set]. OpenAIRE. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14851262>
- [2] The first page was accessed with the following query: https://api.openaire.eu/graph/v1/researchProducts?relOrganizationId=openorgs____%3A%3Aa9607f7a6966af7cc6fa87bf4ab44952&instanceType=Article&fromPublicationDate=2024-01-01&toPublicationDate=2024-12-31&pageSize=100&page=1 (retrieved 3 March 2025).
- [3] OpenAIRE Guidelines for institutional and thematic Repository Managers 4.1, <https://openaire-guidelines-for-literature-repository-managers.readthedocs.io/en/latest/introduction.html>
- [4] Priem, J., Piwowar, H., & Orr, R. (2022). *OpenAlex: A fully-open index of scholarly works, authors, venues, institutions, and concepts*. ArXiv. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2205.01833>
- [5] Willemin, S. (2024). How to improve the metadata coverage and quality of open databases? [PowerPoint slides] *International Open Access Week 2024 in Switzerland, Zurich*. <https://doi.org/10.3929/ethz-b-000709570>

10. Ensure that a guideline with official institution names is accessible and check whether authors use them

Simon Willemin (ETH Library, ETH Zurich)

Description

A guideline on official institution names in local languages and in English, possibly including widespread unofficial names, provides clear guidance for people involved with institutional data, from researchers and academic staff who provide evidence of their affiliations in research contexts, to data engineers working with institutional data. The lack of a guideline or of an official English variant leads to inconsistent naming and increased efforts on the data engineers' side to identify the research output of an institution. In contrast, a guideline with standardized institution names contributes to more consistent naming, which facilitates the identification of its output, ultimately contributing to the enhanced visibility of an institution's research output.

Use case

The Università della Svizzera italiana provides a style guide in Italian and English. It states that the official English name to be used for the institution is "Università della Svizzera italiana", and that the expression "University of Lugano" should not be used [1]. Further unofficial names, such as "University of Italian Switzerland", do not appear explicitly in the style guide.

In order to assess the use of these institution names in the research output of the institution, we use the data from OpenAlex [2] as follows: (a) we extract articles of previous years (2020–2024) attributed to the Università della Svizzera italiana, (b) we remove special characters and accents from the raw affiliation, and (c) we count the number of publications with at least one occurrence of a variant name for each variant from a list containing names of the institution in Italian, English, German and French.

The results of this analysis are presented in Table 1.

Among the 3,576 extracted articles, 3,005 articles have at least one raw affiliation that matches at least one name (up to special characters and accents), and 571 articles do not match any name from the list (i.e., these articles are attributed to the Università della Svizzera italiana in OpenAlex, but the names from the list do not appear in their raw affiliations). The names that appear in the affiliations of most articles correspond to the official names, except for variations in letter case: "Universita della Svizzera italiana" (38.7%), "Universita della Svizzera Italiana" (36.8%). Each considered unofficial English name variant appears in no more than 3.8% of the cases. The most widespread English variants are "University of Lugano" (3.8%) and "University of Italian Switzerland" (2.4%). They are followed by "University of Southern Switzerland" (0.4%). The French and German variants ("Universite de la Suisse italienne", "Universitat der italienischen Schweiz") do not appear in any affiliation of the extracted articles.

The analysis shows that the most widespread names correspond to the official name. Unofficial names also appear in some articles. The analysis may help to determine whether the explicit mention of an unofficial name is relevant to avoiding its future use. In the case of the Università della Svizzera italiana, the inclusion of "University of Lugano" in the guideline aligns with the fact that this is the most widespread unofficial name.

Table 1. Variant names appearing in affiliations attributed to the Università della Svizzera italiana

Variant contained in at least one raw affiliation	Number of articles with variant (full count*)	Proportion of articles
Università della Svizzera italiana	1384	38.7%
Università della Svizzera Italiana	1316	36.8%
University of Lugano	137	3.8%
Università Della Svizzera Italiana	136	3.8%
University of Italian Switzerland	85	2.4%
University of Southern Switzerland	14	0.4%
universita della Svizzera italiana	1	0.0%
Università Della Svizzera italiana	1	0.0%
Università della svizzera italiana	1	0.0%
Universite de la Suisse italienne	0	0.0%
Universität der italienischen Schweiz	0	0.0%

* "full count" means that an article with different variants will be counted as one for each variant it contains. In the table, the second column sums up to 3,075, although 3,005 articles are considered.

Further possible actions

Investigating the articles with unofficial naming may be beneficial. It potentially allows one to determine a source for the non-compliant naming and to apply measures to improve on the proper use in the future. For instance, looking at the raw affiliations of the articles containing "University of Southern Switzerland", one observes that 9 out of 14 articles were published by authors from the same faculty. Such unofficial names may be a sign of the authors being unaware, or could be due to improper semi-automatic entries for the address on a publisher's platform. Addressing this question with the authors, faculty or publisher may lead to more standard institution naming in future research output. The attempt to amend the article with the correct affiliation is commendable, but this may prove difficult due to the lack of flexibility on the publisher's side.

The fact that no article has the French and German name variants may mean that those variants are not in use. It could also be a sign that the affiliation-matching algorithm did not manage to match those variants. Examples of further possible investigation in this regard are given in recommendation 7.

Finally, it might be worthwhile to investigate the 571 articles with no matching names. Some of the cases are due to the coding of special characters, such as "à" corresponding to "x00E0" in Unicode. In our analysis, this has led to raw affiliations transformed in "Universit x00E0 della Svizzera italiana", a variant that was not in the list. The unmatched articles are also due to typos or variant names that were not in our initial list, such as "Università della Svizzera italiana" or "University of the Italian Switzerland." Finally, they are due to names that have been incorrectly attributed to the Università della Svizzera italiana in OpenAlex, such as "Scuola universitaria professionale della Svizzera italiana." In any case, further investigation may lead to improvements regarding the visibility of current and future research output.

Similar concerns hold at the level of faculty and institutes within an institution. Ensuring that a guideline with official names is accessible, communicated to the relevant researchers and staff, and used contributes to greater visibility.

Notes

- [1] Names of USI and USI Faculties, <https://www.desk.usi.ch/en/corporate-design-templates-and-rules> (retrieved 14 March 2025)
- [2] Priem, J., Piwowar, H., & Orr, R. (2022). *OpenAlex: A fully-open index of scholarly works, authors, venues, institutions, and concepts*. ArXiv. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2205.01833>

11. Adopt open author identifiers in institutional databases and ensure widespread adoption among researchers

Barbara Hirschmann (ETH Library, ETH Zurich)

Description

Adopting globally recognized author identifiers in the systems of Swiss HEIs – especially when displaying researchers' profiles or publication data – is crucial for enhancing the visibility of Swiss research output. ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID) provides an established unique identifier for researchers, ensuring that their work is accurately attributed to them, regardless of name variations or institutional changes. In contrast to other author identifiers or profile tools such as Google Scholar, Web of Science ResearcherID or Scopus Author Profiles, ORCID is designed for universal use across disciplines and tools, it allows researchers to have full ownership and control over their profiles and is aiming for compliance with the Principles for Open Scholarly Infrastructure (POSI, [1]). ORCID IDs facilitate the integration of research output across various platforms, making it easier for other researchers, institutions, and funding bodies to discover Swiss researchers' work. By linking publications, datasets, and other research activities to a single ORCID ID, universities can streamline the management of research information, improve the accuracy of reporting, surface connections between different kinds of research output, and enhance the overall impact and reach of their researchers' contributions.

Use case

ETH Zurich has been a member of ORCID since 2017. Our initial aim was to solve the problem of author identification in our institutional repository Research Collection by introducing ORCID as the main author identifier when switching to a new software, since the previous system didn't offer author identifiers at all. This project also led to a collaboration between ETH Library and ETH Zurich's IT Services, enabling an integration between ETH Zurich's Identity and Access Management System (IAM) and ORCID. Early conceptual discussions at this time also involved the question of whether ETH Zurich could potentially mandate ORCID adoption among their researchers – an idea that was not pursued any further. Instead, ORCID adoption is nowadays mainly encouraged by offering features based on ORCID in various ETH systems, as well as by information and outreach resources created by the library.

The following ORCID integrations are offered at ETH Zurich as of 2025:

- Connecting a researcher's ETH profile with their ORCID profile (self-service)
- Displaying ORCID IDs on ETH Zurich's website (in person search and person profiles)
- Importing works from ORCID profiles into the institutional repository Research Collection
- Displaying ORCID IDs on author pages and on PDF cover pages in the institutional repository Research Collection
- Using ORCID IDs within the web CMS as a criterion for generating publication lists with Research Collection data on ETH Zurich websites.

Information and outreach resources that are available to researchers include

- a website about ORCID at ETH Zurich hosted by ETH Library [2]
- instructional pages about how to connect an ETH profile with an ORCID profile and use it in the Research Collection [3]
- a tutorial "How to Use" video about ORCID at ETH Zurich [4]
- a promotional video about the advantages of ORCID for ETH researchers [5]

Table 1 shows the number of ETH members who had connected their ETH profile to an ORCID profile by the end of each year, as well as the number of ETH publications with at least one author, editor or examiner with an ORCID ID in the Research Collection in a certain publication year.

Table 1. Uptake of ORCID at ETH Zurich between 2021 and 2024

Year	Number of ETH profiles connected to ORCID	Percentage of RC records with at least one ORCID ID within this publication year
2021	2872	56%
2022	3699	63%
2023	4539	67%
2024	5328	67%

Considering that ETH Zurich has around 7400 scientific staff members [6], we consider our adoption strategy a success. A significant further increase in ORCID adoption could probably only be achieved if ETH Zurich considered a mandate for ORCID registration. However, ETH Zurich probably also profits from the fact that in the STM discipline most scientific publishers have already moved to mandating ORCID IDs for corresponding authors. This leads to a "de facto" ORCID mandate for many ETH authors, which also significantly drives ORCID adoption. Institutions with different publication cultures might not profit from this development on a similar scale.

Discussion

Based on our experiences, and considering the widespread benefits in terms of researcher visibility, we recommend that Swiss higher-education institutions make a conscious decision about which strategy to follow for adopting ORCID within their institution. The strategy should aim to

- ensure widespread adoption of ORCID IDs among the HEI's researchers,
- establish usage of ORCID IDs in the HEI's systems and databases,
- enable propagation of researchers' ORCID IDs into external systems, such as academic search engines,

and take into consideration aspects, such as

- Current adoption level: How many researchers already have an ORCID profile?
- Institutional culture: How open are the HEI's administration and faculty towards mandatory measures?
- Existing processes and infrastructure: Which processes and tools at the HEI would potentially benefit most from ORCID adoption in terms of data quality or efficiency? In which ones would ORCID adoption be a potential "quick win"?

Usually, an adoption strategy will include technical as well as outreach activities, such as:

- Secure stakeholder support by including faculty, IT staff and administrative departments, to build a strategic plan for ORCID integration.
- Configure university systems to connect with the ORCID registry via the ORCID API. This could include identity-management systems, institutional repositories, data-management systems, grant-application systems, web-content-management systems, and current-research-information systems (CRIS).
- Ensure that ORCID IDs are collected through authenticated processes to avoid misattribution.
- Ensure that ORCID IDs are prominently displayed in university systems, websites and publications.
- Enable researchers to import works or other information from their ORCID profiles to university systems, as well as to send publication data to their ORCID profiles.
- Conduct awareness campaigns, workshops and training sessions to educate researchers about the benefits of ORCID IDs (see recommendation 14).
- Provide support as well as resources such as step-by-step guides and FAQs to help researchers create and manage their ORCID profiles and connect them with the HEI's systems.

Some of the actions mentioned above will require an institutional ORCID membership [7].

Further possible actions

When an institution has already reached a good adoption level, they might want additionally to consider one or more of the following actions and advanced technical integrations:

- Consider curating data on researchers' ORCID records on their behalf: HEIs can add validated assertions about researcher affiliations and work to their ORCID records.
- Make sure ORCID IDs are published in standardized metadata formats via open APIs, for example as author-metadata attributes in repositories or when registering DOIs for publications. This enables external tools to pick the information up and use it, for example, for automatically populating researcher profiles, building citation graphs, and more (see recommendation 1).
- Require ORCID IDs for key processes, such as thesis submissions, grant applications and faculty evaluations. While an overall mandate for ORCID adoption by all researchers at an institution might be difficult to achieve, requiring ORCID IDs for certain processes (potentially including an opt-out option) might be a more feasible goal for which to aim [8].

Notes

- [1] POSI, <https://info.orcid.org/orcids-self-assessment-of-the-posi-principles/> (retrieved 14 March 2025)
- [2] Website about ORCID at ETH Zurich, <https://library.ethz.ch/orcid>
- [3] Instructional pages about ORCID at ETH Zurich, <https://unlimited.ethz.ch/x/xQiSCw>
- [4] Three steps to using ORCID successfully at ETH Zurich, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Ktnrzbs6MTY>
- [5] ORCID iD @ ETH Library, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Qw5vHQ2HIkA>
- [6] ETH Zurich: Personnel figures, <https://ethz.ch/en/the-eth-zurich/working-teaching-and-research/personalkennzahlen.html> (retrieved 14 March 2025)
- [7] ORCID membership, <https://info.orcid.org/membership/> (retrieved 11 March 2025)
- [8] The text in the "Description", "Discussion" and "Further possible actions" parts of this document were partly drafted with the help of Microsoft Copilot (<https://copilot.cloud.microsoft/>) on 28 February 2025. Copilot pointed to the following websites as sources: <https://www.orcidus.lyrasis.org/2025/03/03/orcid-us-implementation-guide/>; <https://info.orcid.org/documentation/integration-best-practices/>; <https://info.orcid.org/jump-starting-orcid-adoption-and-integration-in-the-university-community/>

12. Foster (semi-)automatic publishing of green Open Access (OA) articles at embargo expiration through institutional repositories

Gernot Pruschak (Institute for Applied Data Science & Finance, Business School, Bern University of Applied Sciences)

Description

Researchers nowadays have several OA publishing options at their disposal. Diamond OA refers to outlets that exclusively publish OA articles without charging either authors or readers. Gold OA outlets also solely publish OA articles, but require authors to pay article-processing charges (APCs). Hybrid OA outlets publish both paywalled and OA articles, with APCs required if authors opt for OA. With Green OA, articles are made publicly available through separate repositories, typically after an embargo period [1].

At the beginning, authors had to resort to international platforms like ResearchGate or Academia.edu through the Green OA model [2]. Nowadays, most research and higher-education institutions provide their own repositories for depositing published articles. Examples include UZH's ZORA (Zurich Open Repository and Archive), UNIL's Serval (SERVeur Académique Lausannois) and BFH's ARBOR (Applied Research Bern Open Repository). However, simply setting up such a repository only constitutes a necessary condition for effective Green OA publishing – yet, it does not guarantee success on its own. In order to fully elicit the Green OA power of institutional repositories, two additional steps are required. First, repository managers must ensure that authors keep the repository data up-to-date by inserting information on each publication. Second, institutions must match the publication data available in the repository with the relevant embargo terms and period. The Bern University of Applied Sciences (BFH) fosters Green OA through the implementation of both steps.

Use case

Given their research and teaching commitments, most researchers can only spend limited time and resources on administrative tasks [3]. Moreover, they often regard these administrative tasks as “burdensome and tedious” [4: 26]. Consequently, it is essential to make their interactions with institutional repositories as seamless and efficient as possible. This highlights the importance of incorporating a user experience (UX) design approach when developing new or updating repository interfaces [5].

When the BFH rolled out its new version of ARBOR, the Open Science office conducted in-depth prototype testing with an interdisciplinary set of researchers. In so doing, they distributed links to a preliminary version, asking researchers to update their personal data and upload their most recent publication. The re-

searchers then provided feedback on any challenges they encountered while completing these tasks.

While intuitive and easy-to-navigate interfaces lower barriers for researchers to engage with institutional repositories, it is equally important to encourage researchers to access these repositories in the first place. At the BFH, like at several other institutions, publication data for research evaluation purposes are sourced exclusively from the institutional repository. As a result, researchers who fail to upload their publications to ARBOR miss out on potential research-evaluation benefits at the individual, institute and faculty level. Consequently, this policy incentivizes academic leaders, such as institute heads and deans, to ensure that their teams keep their repository data up-to-date. Therefore, they

actively inform new employees about the importance of the institutional repository during the onboarding and remind them in regular e-mail and intranet updates.

Once authors add a publication to the institutional repository, the ARBOR team of the BFH carefully verifies its metadata, including its OA status and, if applicable, the relevant embargo terms and periods. If a publication is categorized as diamond, gold or hybrid OA, it is already freely accessible upon publication. However, if the publication does not fall into one of these categories, the ARBOR team manually reviews the embargo terms that apply to it. To determine the applicable embargo terms and period, the team consults multiple sources, including author contracts, transitional agreements negotiated by the Consortium of Swiss Academic Libraries, publisher and journal websites, and information available through the Open Policy Finder [6].

As soon as the embargo period expires, the ARBOR team makes the article publicly accessible as Green OA according to the respective publishing terms. This ensures compliance with institutional and publisher policies while maximizing the visibility of the research output.

Discussion

This use case demonstrates the added values arising from the implementation of UX design methods in the development of institutional repositories. However, in terms of the second step, identifying embargo terms and periods, the manual process of scanning author contracts, transitional agreements, publisher and journal websites and Open Policy Finder data is both time-consuming and labor-intensive. While this approach is still feasible at BFH, given its relatively small size compared to other Swiss universities, it becomes increasingly impractical for larger research and higher-education institutions with several thousand researchers. As a result, there exists a pressing need for a dedicated database similar to the Open Policy Finder but specifically tailored to Swiss institutions or for an inclusion of Swiss data in the Open Policy Finder.

Further possible actions

Concerning the (further) developments of institutional repositories, we recommend leveraging Figma for prototype testing. Because Figma allows for quick and easy modifications of the interfaces without requiring a fully developed backend, it offers a cost-effective and flexible solution for enhancing the UX design process. Additionally, user testing could be enhanced through interactive one-on-one sessions, where a member of the Open Science, library or development team meets virtually with a researcher, observing their actions and recording their feedback in real time as they complete the tasks.

To enhance the availability of Green OA, we recommend supporting the current initiative aiming at anchoring a second publication right in Switzerland. More information is available at the project website [7]. Moreover, authors must be reminded to upload not only the published texts, but also the proofs/accepted versions of their publications to the repository, as several journals only allow the Green OA publication of pre-final versions.

Last, the Open Policy Finder solely includes information on the situation in the United Kingdom as it is hosted by the Joint Information Systems Committee (Jisc). Consequently, several of the listed embargo terms and periods do not apply to publications associated with Swiss institutions. To address this gap, we propose that Open Science offices, libraries and institutional repository teams across Swiss research and higher-education institutions collaborate to develop an open database containing embargo terms and periods for all publication outlets in which Swiss-affiliated researchers publish. Establishing such a centralized resource would significantly reduce the administrative burden associated with enabling Green OA, as many researchers in Switzerland are likely to target the same publication outlets multiple times. To further increase efficiency, the database should incorporate an API solution similar to the one offered by the Open Policy Finder [8], allowing for the automatic retrieval of embargo periods. By integrating this functionality, institutions could automate much of the embargo verification process, ensuring that information remains up-to-date while minimizing manual workload.

Notes

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- [8] Jisc. (2025). *Sherpa Legacy API Documentation*. https://openpolicyfinder.jisc.ac.uk/sherpa_legacy_api.pdf (retrieved 22 April 2025)

13. Turn your institutional repository into a service instead of just a platform

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Description

Most higher-education institutions (HEIs) have an institutional repository (IR) to archive, display and share research output, typically managed by research libraries. When implementing such IRs, one could imagine two extremes when it comes to the upload of research output and the curation of the related metadata. One extreme would be a rather technical solution – a platform – allowing researchers to upload their research output without metadata enrichment and quality control by repository managers. The other extreme would be a fully integrated service in which the library takes over as much of the work as possible and aims for a complete bibliography for all researchers of an institute, research output described with rich and complete metadata, and a high Open Access (OA) rate of research output. Even when relying on automatic and semi-automated processes, such an IR requires considerable input and maintenance from repository managers, and for this reason we call it a “service-oriented repository”. While requiring these resources can limit the implementation of such repositories, we advocate for them here due to their ability to improve the visibility of researchers, their research output and, eventually, the visibility of HEIs.

Use case

The Digital Object Repository At the 4 Research Institutes (DORA 4RI – not to be confused with the DORA Declaration) is the common framework for the IRs of the four Swiss research institutes: Eawag, Empa, PSI and WSL (from here on called 4RI); it is operated and maintained by their joint library, Lib4RI. The goal of DORA is to be a service-oriented repository, as described above, while minimizing the amount of input and effort needed from researchers.

To achieve this goal, we leverage (semi-)automated metadata enrichment from external sources and use manual input and quality control by librarians and repository managers where necessary. In Figure 1, we outline the workflow for research-output upload and metadata ingestion according to these principles. The initial metadata ingestion into DORA typically relies on harvested data from external scientific literature databases and is crucial to achieving a complete bibliography. Manual ingestion by researchers is optional and the required number of metadata that researchers must provide in such cases is kept minimal. In the next step, the initial metadata are enriched with information from a range of trusted sources. This includes detailed affiliation data (source: internal Human Resources), funding information (sources: Scopus, funder databases), related research data (source: Data-Cite), citation data (sources: Crossref, Scopus, Web of Science,

Altmetric) and other available metadata (sources: for PubMed, RCSB Protein DB, and others). Additionally, we use authority files for researchers and journals to improve their identification (for example, after name changes) and to support disambiguation. The published version of the research output (source: publisher) and all these metadata are combined into one entry for DORA. This entry undergoes internal quality control by repository managers at Lib4RI before it is released and the 4RI authors of this research output can give feedback.

For closed-access publications, 4RI researchers receive a notification to provide their accepted version that automatically becomes OA at the end of the journal’s embargo period (see also recommendation 12); two additional notifications remind researchers about this step. This workflow contributes to a 90% OA rate for DORA-listed journal articles [1]. Feedback from researchers shows a high satisfaction with the service that DORA provides, including the OA reminders.

While implementing all these steps requires considerable time and effort, each individual step is in our experience helpful to achieve a complete bibliography, to improve the acceptance of researchers for an IR and to increase the visibility of their research outputs.

Figure 1.

Exemplary scheme for the workflow of a service-oriented institutional repository for research output. Most metadata are provided by external databases and require no input from researchers. Quality control is done by repository managers. The main tasks for researchers (highlighted in bold red) are limited to providing the accepted version of their research output (if the published version is not OA already) and feedback with a focus on authors' names and affiliations.

To increase visibility, 4RI researchers can easily display their DORA-listed research output on their personal and/or their institutional website (supported by a full bibliography). Cross-referencing research output over different websites contributes to search-engine optimization (SEO), and hence visibility of research output. By being accessible to external harvesters, DORA-listed research output becomes accessible to relevant scientific databases, such as Unpaywall. Finally, we use our IR as an important source for a range of bibliometric analyses for individual researchers and research units. Such analyses include identifying researchers or research units with low OA rates and our support for making their research output OA where possible.

Further possible actions

We will soon release a new version of DORA with improved features for visibility of research output. These include the incorporation of ORCIDiDs (see also recommendation 11) and a better user experience on mobile devices. These features will support researchers in highlighting their research on social media, thereby increasing the visibility of the research output. In parallel, we aim to increase our use of open databases (for example, OpenAlex) and to become compatible with OpenAIRE metadata standards (see also recommendation 2). In so doing, we will come closer to our goals for DORA to function as a service-oriented IR that complies with Open Science principles.

Note

- [1] Konstantaki, L. A., Last, S., & Nunnenmacher, L. (2022). How to reach > 90% Open Access. [Poster], *Open-Access-Tag*, Bern. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7038052>

14. Train and consult researchers about strategies to increase their research visibility

Michael Bachmann (Lib4RI – Library for the Research Institutes within the ETH Domain: Eawag, Empa, PSI & WSL)

Description

Many strategies and tools exist for researchers to improve the visibility of research output. Collaborations, presenting at conferences and writing literature reviews remain valid methods to increase the visibility of one's research. At the same time, Open Science policies have led to changes and opportunities for the assessment and visibility of researchers and their research outputs. These developments were paralleled by the rise of social media and their use by researchers to promote their work [1]. However, navigating all these possibilities to improve the visibility of research output requires clear guidance for researchers on how to use and prioritize them when facing limited time resources. Training on these topics, making researchers aware of these possibilities and offering relevant information can be important cornerstones of higher education and research institutions, helping researchers to improve the visibility of their research output.

Use case

Lib4RI is the research library for the four Swiss research institutes, Eawag, Empa, PSI and WSL. As part of our service, we train, consult and inform researchers about all aspects of the scientific publishing process. The increased emphasis and implementation of Open Science policies emerged as an important topic in our training efforts. Many of these topics also have direct implications for the visibility of researchers and their research output, causing researchers to ask for support and advice. Research libraries such as Lib4RI are well-positioned to address these questions. Due to our expertise in topics such as Open Access (OA) publishing, unique identifiers and bibliometrics, we are also competent to advise and consult researchers on how to leverage these topics to increase the visibility of their research output (see Table 1).

To maximize access to our training efforts, we implemented a multi-channel training model that combines in-person lectures, webinars, info sheets, website content and special events, such as lectures and workshops. Both the content of this training and the delivery method are constantly adapted according to the needs of researchers. Table 1 provides an overview of both our current and future training efforts for increasing the visibility of research output.

Many of these topics are already addressed in existing training efforts at the respective institutions and their libraries. We propose that bundling the locally available efforts and highlighting their relevance for the visibility of both researchers and their research output is easy to implement for the respective higher-education and research institutions. Such bundling can be as easy as a dedicated section on the respective websites of institutions or their libraries, linking to the respective resources. Taking such actions also highlights the additional value that such training offers, eventually increasing the researchers' interest and acceptance. To improve participation of researchers for these measures, we also recommend announcing and advertising them within the framework of the communication strategy of the library or the respective institution organizing these actions.

Table 1. Covered topics, their impact on research output visibility and the respective efforts implemented at Lib4RI.

Topic	Efforts at Lib4RI for researchers
Unique identifiers (e.g., DOI, ORCID)	Explained and highlighted in training courses [2]; highlighted on website: "Increase your visibility" [3]; consultation; (see also recommendation 11);
Open Access, copyright and CC licenses	Dedicated training session twice per year [2]; extensively covered on website [4, 5]; several info sheets [6]; lectures; consultation with topical experts;
Institutional repository	Increasing share of OA publications by identifying potential for Green OA and motivating researchers to self-archive [7] (see also recommendation 12);
Bibliometrics	Highlighted service on webpage [8] for both standardized and personalized bibliometric analysis; consultation by topical experts;
Scientific writing	Covered in several training courses [2]; writing workshop in 2025;
Social media	Best practices explained and highlighted in training courses [2];
Private website / personal website at institute	Workshops in 2025 explaining benefits, how to easily set up a personal website, and integration of publication list;
Preprints	Consultation; website content will be updated in 2025;

Further possible actions

As mentioned above, presenting one's research output at conferences remains an important strategy to increase visibility. This includes oral presentation skills, but also preparation of clear, appealing and informative figures and presentation slides. Most higher-education and research institutions offer courses for these topics and can easily combine them into a bundled program for improving research visibility. Additional measures could include the preparation of a "visibility toolkit" highlighting relevant tools and step-by-step guides on their use, a "visibility report" in the form of a periodic analysis based on bibliometric features and online visibility, and a strengthened collaboration with the institutional communication department. Given that the training efforts

described here are of interest to all Swiss HEIs and their researchers, it would also be of interest to bundle these resources for several institutions, or even at national level. Similar initiatives exist, for example, for Open Research Data (ORD) and Research Data Management (RDM): The ETH Domain Data Management Campus creates training modules about ORD and RDM (for example, [9]) for all institutions in the ETH domain, but which are openly available to all other Swiss HEIs. A similar initiative can be envisioned for training modules about research visibility.

Notes

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- [2] Overview of training courses at Lib4RI: <https://www.lib4ri.ch/trainings>
- [3] Website content at Lib4RI on how to improve visibility for researchers and their research output: <https://www.lib4ri.ch/increase-your-visibility>
- [4] Website content at Lib4RI regarding OA: <https://www.lib4ri.ch/open-access>
- [5] Website content at Lib4RI regarding Copyright and CC licenses: <https://www.lib4ri.ch/copyright-cc-licences>
- [6] Overview of info sheets at Lib4RI: <https://www.lib4ri.ch/info-sheets-videos>
- [7] Website content at Lib4RI regarding green OA: <https://www.lib4ri.ch/green-open-access>
- [8] Website content at Lib4RI regarding bibliometrics: <https://www.lib4ri.ch/bibliometrics>
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Indexes

The index refers to the corresponding recommendation number. If there is no direct reference to the project or institution in the recommendation, but the author or topic is linked to it, the recommendation number is shown in brackets.

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Swiss Higher Education institutions, research organizations, and consortium

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 Consortium of Swiss Academic Libraries: (2), 12
 ETH Domain: 13
 ETH Zurich (repository: ETH Research Collection): 1, 6, (7), 8, 9, (10), 11
 FHNW University of Applied Sciences and Arts Northwestern Switzerland: 3
 HFR Freiburg Kantonsspital: 7
 HSG University of St.Gallen (institutional repository: Alexandria): 4
 Lib4RI Lib4RI – Library for the Research Institutes within the ETH Domain: Eawag, Empa, PSI & WSL (institutional repository: DORA 4RI): 13, 14
 PHSG Pädagogische Hochschule St.Gallen (institutional repository: #Proforis): (2), 5, 8
 UNIBE University of Bern: (8)
 UNIFR University of Fribourg: 7
 UNIL University of Lausanne (institutional repository: Serval): 12
 UNILU University of Lucerne: 9
 UNINE University of Neuchâtel: 9
 USI Università della Svizzera italiana: 10
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Impressum

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